

Auxiliary Material on the Simulation of EFT Signal Samples With the Amplitude Decomposition Approach

Stefanie Todt

Institut für Kern- und Teilchenphysik, TU Dresden

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This document presents auxiliary material for the study and validation of the amplitude decomposition approach available in the MADGRAPH5_AMC@NLO event generation programme [1]. It is employed for the simulation of dimension-eight Effective Field Theory (EFT) effects of the electroweak sector in the $W^\pm W^\pm jj$ final state based on the model in Ref. [2, 3]. The amplitude decomposition approach allows to generate the individual terms of the EFT extension of the Standard Model (SM).

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1 Additional Observables Comparing the EFT Contributions with the SM

1.1 Loose Region

Figure 1: Kinematic distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system and tagging jets for different values of the f_{S02}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the transverse momentum of the leading lepton $p_T(l_1)$ (a), its pseudorapidity $\eta(l_1)$ (b), the transverse momentum of the leading jet $p_T(j_1)$ (c), and its rapidity $Y(j_1)$ (d). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements at particle level. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow. The first bin includes the underflow if appropriate.

Figure 2: Invariant (transverse) mass distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system for different values of the f_{S02}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the invariant mass of the leading lepton pair, $m_{\ell\ell}$ (a), the transverse masses m_{01} (b) and m_{1T} (c), and the vectorial mass, m_{vec} (d) as defined in [4]. The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements at particle level. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 3: Kinematic distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system for different values of the f_{S02}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the azimuthal angle between the two leading leptons $\Delta\Phi_{ll}$ (a), the sum of the transverse momenta of the two leading neutrinos (b), the lepton centrality ζ (c), and the Zeppenfeld variable for the leading lepton $z(l_1)$ (d). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements at particle level. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow. The first bin includes the underflow if appropriate.

Figure 4: Kinematic distributions related to the tagging jets for different values of the f_{S02}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the invariant mass of the tagging jet system, m_{jj} (a), their rapidity separation ΔY_{jj} (b), and the number of jets in the event $N(j)$ (c). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements at particle level. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 5: Kinematic distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system and tagging jets for different values of the f_{S1}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the transverse momentum of the leading lepton $p_T(l_1)$ (a), its pseudorapidity $\eta(l_1)$ (b), the transverse momentum of the leading jet $p_T(j_1)$ (c), and its rapidity $Y(j_1)$ (d). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow. The first bin includes the underflow if appropriate.

Figure 6: Invariant (transverse) mass distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system for different values of the f_{S1}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the invariant mass of the leading lepton pair, $m_{\ell\ell}$ (a), the transverse masses m_{o1} (b) and m_{1T} (c), and the vectorial mass, m_{vec} (d) as defined in [4]. The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 7: Kinematic distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system for different values of the f_{S1}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the azimuthal angle between the two leading leptons $\Delta\Phi_{ll}$ (a), the sum of the transverse momenta of the two leading neutrinos (b), the lepton centrality ζ (c), and the Zeppenfeld variable for the leading lepton $z(l_1)$ (d). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 8: Kinematic distributions related to the tagging jets for different values of the f_{S1}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the invariant mass of the tagging jet system, m_{jj} (a), their rapidity separation ΔY_{jj} (b), and the number of jets in the event $N(j)$ (c). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 9: Kinematic distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system and tagging jets for different values of the f_{M0}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the transverse momentum of the leading lepton $p_T(l_1)$ (a), its pseudorapidity $\eta(l_1)$ (b), the rapidity of the leading jet $Y(j_1)$ (c), and the number of jets in the event $N(j)$ (d). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow. The first bin includes the underflow if appropriate.

Figure 10: Invariant (transverse) mass distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system for different values of the f_{M0}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the invariant mass of the leading lepton pair, $m_{\ell\ell}$ (a), the transverse masses m_{o1} (b) and m_{1T} (c), and the vectorial mass, m_{vec} (d) as defined in [4]. The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 11: Kinematic distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system for different values of the f_{M0}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the azimuthal angle between the two leading leptons $\Delta\Phi_{ll}$ (a), the sum of the transverse momenta of the two leading neutrinos (b), the lepton centrality ζ (c), and the Zeppenfeld variable for the leading lepton $z(l_1)$ (d). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow. The first bin includes the underflow if appropriate.

Figure 12: Kinematic distributions related to the tagging jets for different values of the f_{M0}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the invariant mass of the tagging jet system, m_{jj} (a), their rapidity separation ΔY_{jj} (b), and the number of jets in the event $N(j)$ (c). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow. The first bin includes the underflow if appropriate.

Figure 13: Kinematic distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system and tagging jets for different values of the f_{M1}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the transverse momentum of the leading lepton $p_T(l_1)$ (a), its pseudorapidity $\eta(l_1)$ (b), the transverse momentum of the leading jet $p_T(j_1)$ (c), and its rapidity $Y(j_1)$ (d). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow. The first bin includes the underflow if appropriate.

Figure 14: Invariant (transverse) mass distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system for different values of the f_{M1}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the invariant mass of the leading lepton pair, $m_{\ell\ell}$ (a), the transverse masses m_{o1} (b) and m_{1T} (c), and the vectorial mass, m_{vec} (d) as defined in [4]. The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 15: Kinematic distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system for different values of the f_{M1}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the azimuthal angle between the two leading leptons $\Delta\Phi_{ll}$ (a), the sum of the transverse momenta of the two leading neutrinos (b), the lepton centrality ζ (c), and the Zeppenfeld variable for the leading lepton $z(l_1)$ (d). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow. The first bin includes the underflow if appropriate.

Figure 16: Kinematic distributions related to the tagging jets for different values of the f_{M1}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the invariant mass of the tagging jet system, m_{jj} (a), their rapidity separation ΔY_{jj} (b), and the number of jets in the event $N(j)$ (c). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 17: Kinematic distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system and tagging jets for different values of the f_{M7}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the transverse momentum of the leading lepton $p_T(l_1)$ (a), its pseudorapidity $\eta(l_1)$ (b), the transverse momentum of the leading jet $p_T(j_1)$ (c), and its rapidity $Y(j_1)$ (d). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow. The first bin includes the underflow if appropriate.

Figure 18: Invariant (transverse) mass distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system for different values of the f_{M7}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the invariant mass of the leading lepton pair, $m_{\ell\ell}$ (a), the transverse masses m_{o1} (b) and m_{1T} (c), and the vectorial mass, m_{vec} (d) as defined in [4]. The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 19: Kinematic distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system for different values of the f_{M7}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the azimuthal angle between the two leading leptons $\Delta\Phi_{ll}$ (a), the sum of the transverse momenta of the two leading neutrinos (b), the lepton centrality ζ (c), and the Zeppenfeld variable for the leading lepton $z(l_1)$ (d). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow. The first bin includes the underflow if appropriate.

Figure 20: Kinematic distributions related to the tagging jets for different values of the f_{M7}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the invariant mass of the tagging jet system, m_{jj} (a), their rapidity separation ΔY_{jj} (b), and the number of jets in the event $N(j)$ (c). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 21: Kinematic distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system and tagging jets for different values of the f_{T0}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the transverse momentum of the leading lepton $p_T(l_1)$ (a), its pseudorapidity $\eta(l_1)$ (b), the rapidity of the leading jet $Y(j_1)$ (c), and the number of jets in the event $N(j)$ (d). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow. The first bin includes the underflow if appropriate.

Figure 22: Invariant (transverse) mass distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system for different values of the f_{T0}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the invariant mass of the leading lepton pair, $m_{\ell\ell}$ (a), the transverse masses m_{o1} (b) and m_{1T} (c), and the vectorial mass, m_{vec} (d) as defined in [4]. The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 23: Kinematic distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system for different values of the f_{T0}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the azimuthal angle between the two leading leptons $\Delta\Phi_{ll}$ (a), the sum of the transverse momenta of the two leading neutrinos (b), the lepton centrality ζ (c), and the Zeppenfeld variable for the leading lepton $z(l_1)$ (d). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow. The first bin includes the underflow if appropriate.

Figure 24: Kinematic distributions related to the tagging jets for different values of the f_{T0}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the invariant mass of the tagging jet system, m_{jj} (a), their rapidity separation ΔY_{jj} (b), and the number of jets in the event $N(j)$ (c). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 25: Kinematic distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system and tagging jets for different values of the f_{T1}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the transverse momentum of the leading lepton $p_T(l_1)$ (a), its pseudorapidity $\eta(l_1)$ (b), the transverse momentum of the leading jet $p_T(j_1)$ (c), and its rapidity $Y(j_1)$ (d). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow. The first bin includes the underflow if appropriate.

Figure 26: Invariant (transverse) mass distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system for different values of the f_{T1}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the invariant mass of the leading lepton pair, $m_{\ell\ell}$ (a), the transverse masses m_{o1} (b) and m_{1T} (c), and the vectorial mass, m_{vec} (d) as defined in [4]. The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 27: Kinematic distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system for different values of the f_{T1}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the azimuthal angle between the two leading leptons $\Delta\Phi_{ll}$ (a), the sum of the transverse momenta of the two leading neutrinos (b), the lepton centrality ζ (c), and the Zeppenfeld variable for the leading lepton $z(l_1)$ (d). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow. The first bin includes the underflow if appropriate.

Figure 28: Kinematic distributions related to the tagging jets for different values of the f_{T1}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the invariant mass of the tagging jet system, m_{jj} (a), their rapidity separation ΔY_{jj} (b), and the number of jets in the event $N(j)$ (c). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 29: Kinematic distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system and tagging jets for different values of the f_{T2}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the transverse momentum of the leading lepton $p_T(l_1)$ (a), its pseudorapidity $\eta(l_1)$ (b), the transverse momentum of the leading jet $p_T(j_1)$ (c), and its rapidity $Y(j_1)$ (d). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow. The first bin includes the underflow if appropriate.

Figure 30: Invariant (transverse) mass distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system for different values of the f_{T2}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the invariant mass of the leading lepton pair, $m_{\ell\ell}$ (a), the transverse masses m_{o1} (b) and m_{1T} (c), and the vectorial mass, m_{vec} (d) as defined in [4]. The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 31: Kinematic distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system for different values of the f_{T2}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the azimuthal angle between the two leading leptons $\Delta\Phi_{ll}$ (a), the sum of the transverse momenta of the two leading neutrinos (b), the lepton centrality ζ (c), and the Zeppenfeld variable for the leading lepton $z(l_1)$ (d). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow. The first bin includes the underflow if appropriate.

Figure 32: Kinematic distributions related to the tagging jets for different values of the f_{T2}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the invariant mass of the tagging jet system, m_{jj} (a), their rapidity separation ΔY_{jj} (b), and the number of jets in the event $N(j)$ (c). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

1.2 Fiducial Region

Figure 33: Kinematic distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system and tagging jets for different values of the f_{S02}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the transverse momentum of the leading lepton $p_T(l_1)$ (a), its pseudorapidity $\eta(l_1)$ (b), the transverse momentum of the leading jet $p_T(j_1)$ (c), and its rapidity $Y(j_1)$ (d). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in the fiducial region of Ref. [5] at particle level. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow. The first bin includes the underflow if appropriate.

Figure 34: Invariant (transverse) mass distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system for different values of the f_{S02}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the invariant mass of the leading lepton pair, m_{ll} (a), the transverse masses m_{o1} (b) and m_{1T} (c), and the vectorial mass, m_{vec} (d) as defined in [4]. The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in the fiducial region of Ref. [5] at particle level. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 35: Kinematic distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system for different values of the f_{S02}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the azimuthal angle between the two leading leptons $\Delta\Phi_{ll}$ (a), the sum of the transverse momenta of the two leading neutrinos (b), the lepton centrality ζ (c), and the Zeppenfeld variable for the leading lepton $z(l_1)$ (d). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in the fiducial region of Ref. [5] at particle level. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow. The first bin includes the underflow if appropriate.

Figure 36: Kinematic distributions related to the tagging jets for different values of the f_{S02}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the invariant mass of the tagging jet system, m_{jj} (a), their rapidity separation ΔY_{jj} (b), and the number of jets in the event $N(j)$ (c). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in the fiducial region of Ref. [5] at particle level. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 37: Kinematic distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system and tagging jets for different values of the f_{S1}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the transverse momentum of the leading lepton $p_T(l_1)$ (a), its pseudorapidity $\eta(l_1)$ (b), the transverse momentum of the leading jet $p_T(j_1)$ (c), and its rapidity $Y(j_1)$ (d). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in the fiducial region of Ref. [5] at particle level. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow. The first bin includes the underflow if appropriate.

Figure 38: Invariant (transverse) mass distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system for different values of the f_{S1}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the invariant mass of the leading lepton pair, $m_{\ell\ell}$ (a), the transverse masses m_{o1} (b) and m_{1T} (c), and the vectorial mass, m_{vec} (d) as defined in [4]. The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in the fiducial region of Ref. [5] at particle level. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 39: Kinematic distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system for different values of the f_{S1}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the azimuthal angle between the two leading leptons $\Delta\Phi_{ll}$ (a), the sum of the transverse momenta of the two leading neutrinos (b), the lepton centrality ζ (c), and the Zeppenfeld variable for the leading lepton $z(l_1)$ (d). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in the fiducial region of Ref. [5] at particle level. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow. The first bin includes the underflow if appropriate.

Figure 40: Kinematic distributions related to the tagging jets for different values of the f_{S1}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the invariant mass of the tagging jet system, m_{jj} (a), their rapidity separation ΔY_{jj} (b), and the number of jets in the event $N(j)$ (c). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in the fiducial region of Ref. [5] at particle level. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 41: Kinematic distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system and tagging jets for different values of the f_{M0}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the transverse momentum of the leading lepton $p_T(l_1)$ (a), its pseudorapidity $\eta(l_1)$ (b), the transverse momentum of the leading jet $p_T(j_1)$ (c), and its rapidity $Y(j_1)$ (d). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in the fiducial region of Ref. [5] at particle level. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow. The first bin includes the underflow if appropriate.

Figure 42: Invariant (transverse) mass distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system for different values of the f_{M0}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the invariant mass of the leading lepton pair, m_{ll} (a), the transverse masses m_{o1} (b) and m_{1T} (c), and the vectorial mass, m_{vec} (d) as defined in [4]. The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in the fiducial region of Ref. [5] at particle level. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 43: Kinematic distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system for different values of the f_{M0}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the azimuthal angle between the two leading leptons $\Delta\Phi_{ll}$ (a), the sum of the transverse momenta of the two leading neutrinos (b), the lepton centrality ζ (c), and the Zeppenfeld variable for the leading lepton $z(l_1)$ (d). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in the fiducial region of Ref. [5] at particle level. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow. The first bin includes the underflow if appropriate.

Figure 44: Kinematic distributions related to the tagging jets for different values of the f_{M0}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the invariant mass of the tagging jet system, m_{jj} (a), their rapidity separation ΔY_{jj} (b), and the number of jets in the event $N(j)$ (c). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in the fiducial region of Ref. [5] at particle level. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 45: Kinematic distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system and tagging jets for different values of the f_{M1}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the transverse momentum of the leading lepton $p_T(l_1)$ (a), its pseudorapidity $\eta(l_1)$ (b), the transverse momentum of the leading jet $p_T(j_1)$ (c), and its rapidity $Y(j_1)$ (d). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in the fiducial region of Ref. [5] at particle level. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow. The first bin includes the underflow if appropriate.

Figure 46: Invariant (transverse) mass distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system for different values of the f_{M1}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the invariant mass of the leading lepton pair, m_{ll} (a), the transverse masses m_{o1} (b) and m_{1T} (c), and the vectorial mass, m_{vec} (d) as defined in [4]. The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in the fiducial region of Ref. [5] at particle level. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 47: Kinematic distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system for different values of the f_{M1}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the azimuthal angle between the two leading leptons $\Delta\Phi_{ll}$ (a), the sum of the transverse momenta of the two leading neutrinos (b), the lepton centrality ζ (c), and the Zeppenfeld variable for the leading lepton $z(l_1)$ (d). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in the fiducial region of Ref. [5] at particle level. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow. The first bin includes the underflow if appropriate.

Figure 48: Kinematic distributions related to the tagging jets for different values of the f_{M1}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the invariant mass of the tagging jet system, m_{jj} (a), their rapidity separation ΔY_{jj} (b), and the number of jets in the event $N(j)$ (c). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in the fiducial region of Ref. [5] at particle level. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 49: Kinematic distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system and tagging jets for different values of the f_{M7}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the transverse momentum of the leading lepton $p_T(l_1)$ (a), its pseudorapidity $\eta(l_1)$ (b), the transverse momentum of the leading jet $p_T(j_1)$ (c), and its rapidity $Y(j_1)$ (d). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in the fiducial region of Ref. [5] at particle level. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow. The first bin includes the underflow if appropriate.

Figure 50: Invariant (transverse) mass distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system for different values of the f_{M7}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the invariant mass of the leading lepton pair, m_{ll} (a), the transverse masses m_{o1} (b) and m_{1T} (c), and the vectorial mass, m_{vec} (d) as defined in [4]. The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in the fiducial region of Ref. [5] at particle level. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 51: Kinematic distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system for different values of the f_{M7}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the azimuthal angle between the two leading leptons $\Delta\Phi_{ll}$ (a), the sum of the transverse momenta of the two leading neutrinos (b), the lepton centrality ζ (c), and the Zeppenfeld variable for the leading lepton $z(l_1)$ (d). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in the fiducial region of Ref. [5] at particle level. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow. The first bin includes the underflow if appropriate.

Figure 52: Kinematic distributions related to the tagging jets for different values of the f_{M7}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the invariant mass of the tagging jet system, m_{jj} (a), their rapidity separation ΔY_{jj} (b), and the number of jets in the event $N(j)$ (c). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in the fiducial region of Ref. [5] at particle level. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 53: Kinematic distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system and tagging jets for different values of the f_{T0}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the transverse momentum of the leading lepton $p_T(l_1)$ (a), its pseudorapidity $\eta(l_1)$ (b), the transverse momentum of the leading jet $p_T(j_1)$ (c), and its rapidity $Y(j_1)$ (d). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in the fiducial region of Ref. [5] at particle level. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow. The first bin includes the underflow if appropriate.

Figure 54: Invariant (transverse) mass distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system for different values of the f_{T0}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the invariant mass of the leading lepton pair, m_{ll} (a), the transverse masses m_{o1} (b) and m_{1T} (c), and the vectorial mass, m_{vec} (d) as defined in [4]. The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in the fiducial region of Ref. [5] at particle level. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 55: Kinematic distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system for different values of the f_{T0}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the azimuthal angle between the two leading leptons $\Delta\Phi_{ll}$ (a), the sum of the transverse momenta of the two leading neutrinos (b), the lepton centrality ζ (c), and the Zeppenfeld variable for the leading lepton $z(l_1)$ (d). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in the fiducial region of Ref. [5] at particle level. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow. The first bin includes the underflow if appropriate.

Figure 56: Kinematic distributions related to the tagging jets for different values of the f_{T0}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the invariant mass of the tagging jet system, m_{jj} (a), their rapidity separation ΔY_{jj} (b), and the number of jets in the event $N(j)$ (c). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in the fiducial region of Ref. [5] at particle level. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 57: Kinematic distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system and tagging jets for different values of the f_{T1}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the transverse momentum of the leading lepton $p_T(l_1)$ (a), its pseudorapidity $\eta(l_1)$ (b), the transverse momentum of the leading jet $p_T(j_1)$ (c), and its rapidity $Y(j_1)$ (d). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in the fiducial region of Ref. [5] at particle level. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow. The first bin includes the underflow if appropriate.

Figure 58: Invariant (transverse) mass distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system for different values of the f_{T1}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the invariant mass of the leading lepton pair, m_{ll} (a), the transverse masses m_{o1} (b) and m_{1T} (c), and the vectorial mass, m_{vec} (d) as defined in [4]. The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in the fiducial region of Ref. [5] at particle level. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 59: Kinematic distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system for different values of the f_{T1}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the azimuthal angle between the two leading leptons $\Delta\Phi_{ll}$ (a), the sum of the transverse momenta of the two leading neutrinos (b), the lepton centrality ζ (c), and the Zeppenfeld variable for the leading lepton $z(l_1)$ (d). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in the fiducial region of Ref. [5] at particle level. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow. The first bin includes the underflow if appropriate.

Figure 60: Kinematic distributions related to the tagging jets for different values of the f_{T1}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the invariant mass of the tagging jet system, m_{jj} (a), their rapidity separation ΔY_{jj} (b), and the number of jets in the event $N(j)$ (c). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in the fiducial region of Ref. [5] at particle level. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 61: Kinematic distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system and tagging jets for different values of the f_{T2}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the transverse momentum of the leading lepton $p_T(l_1)$ (a), its pseudorapidity $\eta(l_1)$ (b), the transverse momentum of the leading jet $p_T(j_1)$ (c), and its rapidity $Y(j_1)$ (d). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in the fiducial region of Ref. [5] at particle level. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow. The first bin includes the underflow if appropriate.

Figure 62: Invariant (transverse) mass distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system for different values of the f_{T2}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the invariant mass of the leading lepton pair, $m_{\ell\ell}$ (a), the transverse masses m_{o1} (b) and m_{1T} (c), and the vectorial mass, m_{vec} (d) as defined in [4]. The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in the fiducial region of Ref. [5] at particle level. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 63: Kinematic distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system for different values of the f_{T2}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the azimuthal angle between the two leading leptons $\Delta\Phi_{ll}$ (a), the sum of the transverse momenta of the two leading neutrinos (b), the lepton centrality ζ (c), and the Zeppenfeld variable for the leading lepton $z(l_1)$ (d). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in the fiducial region of Ref. [5] at particle level. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow. The first bin includes the underflow if appropriate.

Figure 64: Kinematic distributions related to the tagging jets for different values of the f_{T2}/Λ^4 parameter and the SM prediction. Shown are the invariant mass of the tagging jet system, m_{jj} (a), their rapidity separation ΔY_{jj} (b), and the number of jets in the event $N(j)$ (c). The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in the fiducial region of Ref. [5] at particle level. The amplitude decomposition method is used for the EFT distributions. The lower panel shows the ratio of the EFT contributions to the SM prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

2 Validation of the Decomposition Method

Figure 65: Distributions of the transverse momentum $p_T(l_1)$ (a,b) and pseudorapidity $\eta(l_1)$ (c,d) of the leading lepton for the nominal value of the f_{S02}/Λ^4 parameter in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements (a,c) and the fiducial region (b,d). Shown are the SM prediction, the decomposed LIN and QUAD EFT contributions and their sum, labelled SUM, together with the prediction of an independently simulated sample of the full prediction of the SM with the EFT extension, labelled FULL. The lower panel shows the ratio of the SUM with respect to the FULL prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 66: Distributions of the number of jets in the event, $N(j)$ (a,b), and the transverse momentum, $p_T(j_1)$ (c,d), of the leading jet for the nominal value of the f_{S02}/Λ^4 parameter in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements (a,c) and the fiducial region (b,d). Shown are the SM prediction, the decomposed LIN and QUAD EFT contributions and their sum, labelled SUM, together with the prediction of an independently simulated sample of the full prediction of the SM with the EFT extension, labelled FULL. The lower panel shows the ratio of the SUM with respect to the FULL prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 67: Distributions of the invariant mass of the leading lepton pair, m_{ll} (a,b), and the $W^{\pm}W^{\pm}$ system, m_{WW} (c,d), for the nominal value of the f_{S02}/Λ^4 parameter in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements (a,c) and the fiducial region (b,d). Shown are the SM prediction, the decomposed LIN and QUAD EFT contributions and their sum, labelled SUM, together with the prediction of an independently simulated sample of the full prediction of the SM with the EFT extension, labelled FULL. The lower panel shows the ratio of the SUM with respect to the FULL prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 68: Distributions of the invariant mass, m_{jj} (a,b), and rapidity separation, ΔY_{jj} (c,d), of the tagging jet pair for the nominal value of the f_{S02}/Λ^4 parameter in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements (a,c) and the fiducial region (b,d). Shown are the SM prediction, the decomposed LIN and QUAD EFT contributions and their sum, labelled SUM, together with the prediction of an independently simulated sample of the full prediction of the SM with the EFT extension, labelled FULL. The lower panel shows the ratio of the SUM with respect to the FULL prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 69: Distributions of the transverse momentum $p_T(l_1)$ (a,b) and pseudorapidity $\eta(l_1)$ (c,d) of the leading lepton for the nominal value of the f_{S1}/Λ^4 parameter in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements (a,c) and the fiducial region (b,d). Shown are the SM prediction, the decomposed LIN and QUAD EFT contributions and their sum, labelled SUM, together with the prediction of an independently simulated sample of the full prediction of the SM with the EFT extension, labelled FULL. The lower panel shows the ratio of the SUM with respect to the FULL prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 70: Distributions of the number of jets in the event, $N(j)$ (a,b), and the transverse momentum, $p_T(j_1)$ (c,d), of the leading jet for the nominal value of the f_{S1}/Λ^4 parameter in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements (a,c) and the fiducial region (b,d). Shown are the SM prediction, the decomposed LIN and QUAD EFT contributions and their sum, labelled SUM, together with the prediction of an independently simulated sample of the full prediction of the SM with the EFT extension, labelled FULL. The lower panel shows the ratio of the SUM with respect to the FULL prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 71: Distributions of the invariant mass of the leading lepton pair, m_{ll} (a), and the $W^{\pm}W^{\pm}$ system, m_{WW} (b), for the nominal value of the f_{S1}/Λ^4 parameter in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements. Shown are the SM prediction, the decomposed LIN and QUAD EFT contributions and their sum, labelled SUM, together with the prediction of an independently simulated sample of the full prediction of the SM with the EFT extension, labelled FULL. The lower panel shows the ratio of the SUM with respect to the FULL prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 72: Distributions of the invariant mass, m_{jj} (a,b), and rapidity separation, ΔY_{jj} (c,d), of the tagging jet pair for the nominal value of the f_{S1}/Λ^4 parameter in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements (a,c) and the fiducial region (b,d). Shown are the SM prediction, the decomposed LIN and QUAD EFT contributions and their sum, labelled SUM, together with the prediction of an independently simulated sample of the full prediction of the SM with the EFT extension, labelled FULL. The lower panel shows the ratio of the SUM with respect to the FULL prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 73: Distributions of the transverse momentum $p_T(l_1)$ (a,b) and pseudorapidity $\eta(l_1)$ (c,d) of the leading lepton for the nominal value of the f_{M0}/Λ^4 parameter in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements (a,c) and the fiducial region (b,d). Shown are the SM prediction, the decomposed LIN and QUAD EFT contributions and their sum, labelled SUM, together with the prediction of an independently simulated sample of the full prediction of the SM with the EFT extension, labelled FULL. The lower panel shows the ratio of the SUM with respect to the FULL prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 74: Distributions of the number of jets in the event, $N(j)$ (a,b), and the transverse momentum, $p_T(j_1)$ (c,d), of the leading jet for the nominal value of the f_{M0}/Λ^4 parameter in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements (a,c) and the fiducial region (b,d). Shown are the SM prediction, the decomposed LIN and QUAD EFT contributions and their sum, labelled SUM, together with the prediction of an independently simulated sample of the full prediction of the SM with the EFT extension, labelled FULL. The lower panel shows the ratio of the SUM with respect to the FULL prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 75: Distributions of the invariant mass of the leading lepton pair, m_l (a), and the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system, m_{WW} (b), for the nominal value of the f_{M0}/Λ^4 parameter in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements. Shown are the SM prediction, the decomposed LIN and QUAD EFT contributions and their sum, labelled SUM, together with the prediction of an independently simulated sample of the full prediction of the SM with the EFT extension, labelled FULL. The lower panel shows the ratio of the SUM with respect to the FULL prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 76: Distributions of the invariant mass, m_{jj} (a,b), and rapidity separation, ΔY_{jj} (c,d), of the tagging jet pair for the nominal value of the f_{M0}/Λ^4 parameter in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements (a,c) and the fiducial region (b,d). Shown are the SM prediction, the decomposed LIN and QUAD EFT contributions and their sum, labelled SUM, together with the prediction of an independently simulated sample of the full prediction of the SM with the EFT extension, labelled FULL. The lower panel shows the ratio of the SUM with respect to the FULL prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 77: Distributions of the transverse momentum $p_T(l_1)$ (a,b) and pseudorapidity $\eta(l_1)$ (c,d) of the leading lepton for the nominal value of the f_{M1}/Λ^4 parameter in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements (a,c) and the fiducial region (b,d). Shown are the SM prediction, the decomposed LIN and QUAD EFT contributions and their sum, labelled SUM, together with the prediction of an independently simulated sample of the full prediction of the SM with the EFT extension, labelled FULL. The lower panel shows the ratio of the SUM with respect to the FULL prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 78: Distributions of the number of jets in the event, $N(j)$ (a,b), and the transverse momentum, $p_T(j_1)$ (c,d), of the leading jet for the nominal value of the f_{M1}/Λ^4 parameter in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements (a,c) and the fiducial region (b,d). Shown are the SM prediction, the decomposed LIN and QUAD EFT contributions and their sum, labelled SUM, together with the prediction of an independently simulated sample of the full prediction of the SM with the EFT extension, labelled FULL. The lower panel shows the ratio of the SUM with respect to the FULL prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 79: Distributions of the invariant mass of the leading lepton pair, m_{ll} (a,b), and the $W^{\pm}W^{\pm}$ system, m_{WW} (c,d), for the nominal value of the f_{M1}/Λ^4 parameter in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements (a,c) and the fiducial region (b,d). Shown are the SM prediction, the decomposed LIN and QUAD EFT contributions and their sum, labelled SUM, together with the prediction of an independently simulated sample of the full prediction of the SM with the EFT extension, labelled FULL. The lower panel shows the ratio of the SUM with respect to the FULL prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 80: Distributions of the invariant mass, m_{jj} (a,b), and rapidity separation, ΔY_{jj} (c,d), of the tagging jet pair for the nominal value of the f_{M1}/Λ^4 parameter in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements (a,c) and the fiducial region (b,d). Shown are the SM prediction, the decomposed LIN and QUAD EFT contributions and their sum, labelled SUM, together with the prediction of an independently simulated sample of the full prediction of the SM with the EFT extension, labelled FULL. The lower panel shows the ratio of the SUM with respect to the FULL prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 81: Distributions of the transverse momentum $p_T(l_1)$ (a,b) and pseudorapidity $\eta(l_1)$ (c,d) of the leading lepton for the nominal value of the f_{M7}/Λ^4 parameter in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements (a,c) and the fiducial region (b,d). Shown are the SM prediction, the decomposed LIN and QUAD EFT contributions and their sum, labelled SUM, together with the prediction of an independently simulated sample of the full prediction of the SM with the EFT extension, labelled FULL. The lower panel shows the ratio of the SUM with respect to the FULL prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 82: Distributions of the number of jets in the event, $N(j)$ (a,b), and the transverse momentum, $p_T(j_1)$ (c,d), of the leading jet for the nominal value of the f_{M7}/Λ^4 parameter in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements (a,c) and the fiducial region (b,d). Shown are the SM prediction, the decomposed LIN and QUAD EFT contributions and their sum, labelled SUM, together with the prediction of an independently simulated sample of the full prediction of the SM with the EFT extension, labelled FULL. The lower panel shows the ratio of the SUM with respect to the FULL prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 83: Distributions of the invariant mass of the leading lepton pair, m_{ll} (a,b), and the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system, m_{WW} (c,d), for the nominal value of the f_{M7}/Λ^4 parameter in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements (a,c) and the fiducial region (b,d). Shown are the SM prediction, the decomposed LIN and QUAD EFT contributions and their sum, labelled SUM, together with the prediction of an independently simulated sample of the full prediction of the SM with the EFT extension, labelled FULL. The lower panel shows the ratio of the SUM with respect to the FULL prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 84: Distributions of the invariant mass, m_{jj} (a,b), and rapidity separation, ΔY_{jj} (c,d), of the tagging jet pair for the nominal value of the f_{M7}/Λ^4 parameter in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements (a,c) and the fiducial region (b,d). Shown are the SM prediction, the decomposed LIN and QUAD EFT contributions and their sum, labelled SUM, together with the prediction of an independently simulated sample of the full prediction of the SM with the EFT extension, labelled FULL. The lower panel shows the ratio of the SUM with respect to the FULL prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 85: Distributions of the transverse momentum $p_T(l_1)$ (a,b) and pseudorapidity $\eta(l_1)$ (c,d) of the leading lepton for the nominal value of the f_{T0}/Λ^4 parameter in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements (a,c) and the fiducial region (b,d). Shown are the SM prediction, the decomposed LIN and QUAD EFT contributions and their sum, labelled SUM, together with the prediction of an independently simulated sample of the full prediction of the SM with the EFT extension, labelled FULL. The lower panel shows the ratio of the SUM with respect to the FULL prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 86: Distributions of the number of jets in the event, $N(j)$ (a,b), and the transverse momentum, $p_T(j_1)$ (c,d), of the leading jet for the nominal value of the f_{T0}/Λ^4 parameter in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements (a,c) and the fiducial region (b,d). Shown are the SM prediction, the decomposed LIN and QUAD EFT contributions and their sum, labelled SUM, together with the prediction of an independently simulated sample of the full prediction of the SM with the EFT extension, labelled FULL. The lower panel shows the ratio of the SUM with respect to the FULL prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 87: Distributions of the invariant mass of the leading lepton pair, m_{ll} in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements (a), and the invariant mass of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system, m_{WW} in the fiducial region (b), for the nominal value of the f_{T0}/Λ^4 parameter. Shown are the SM prediction, the decomposed LIN and QUAD EFT contributions and their sum, labelled SUM, together with the prediction of an independently simulated sample of the full prediction of the SM with the EFT extension, labelled FULL. The lower panel shows the ratio of the SUM with respect to the FULL prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 88: Distributions of the invariant mass, m_{jj} (a,b), and rapidity separation, ΔY_{jj} (c,d), of the tagging jet pair for the nominal value of the f_{T0}/Λ^4 parameter in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements (a,c) and the fiducial region (b,d). Shown are the SM prediction, the decomposed LIN and QUAD EFT contributions and their sum, labelled SUM, together with the prediction of an independently simulated sample of the full prediction of the SM with the EFT extension, labelled FULL. The lower panel shows the ratio of the SUM with respect to the FULL prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 89: Distributions of the transverse momentum $p_T(l_1)$ (a,b) and pseudorapidity $\eta(l_1)$ (c,d) of the leading lepton for the nominal value of the f_{T1}/Λ^4 parameter in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements (a,c) and the fiducial region (b,d). Shown are the SM prediction, the decomposed LIN and QUAD EFT contributions and their sum, labelled SUM, together with the prediction of an independently simulated sample of the full prediction of the SM with the EFT extension, labelled FULL. The lower panel shows the ratio of the SUM with respect to the FULL prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 90: Distributions of the number of jets in the event, $N(j)$ (a,b), and the transverse momentum, $p_T(j_1)$ (c,d), of the leading jet for the nominal value of the f_{T1}/Λ^4 parameter in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements (a,c) and the fiducial region (b,d). Shown are the SM prediction, the decomposed LIN and QUAD EFT contributions and their sum, labelled SUM, together with the prediction of an independently simulated sample of the full prediction of the SM with the EFT extension, labelled FULL. The lower panel shows the ratio of the SUM with respect to the FULL prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 91: Distributions of the invariant mass of the leading lepton pair, m_{ll} (a,b), and the $W^{\pm}W^{\pm}$ system, m_{WW} (c,d), for the nominal value of the f_{T1}/Λ^4 parameter in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements (a,c) and the fiducial region (b,d). Shown are the SM prediction, the decomposed LIN and QUAD EFT contributions and their sum, labelled SUM, together with the prediction of an independently simulated sample of the full prediction of the SM with the EFT extension, labelled FULL. The lower panel shows the ratio of the SUM with respect to the FULL prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 92: Distributions of the invariant mass, m_{jj} (a,b), and rapidity separation, ΔY_{jj} (c,d), of the tagging jet pair for the nominal value of the f_{T1}/Λ^4 parameter in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements (a,c) and the fiducial region (b,d). Shown are the SM prediction, the decomposed LIN and QUAD EFT contributions and their sum, labelled SUM, together with the prediction of an independently simulated sample of the full prediction of the SM with the EFT extension, labelled FULL. The lower panel shows the ratio of the SUM with respect to the FULL prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 93: Distributions of the transverse momentum $p_T(l_1)$ (a,b) and pseudorapidity $\eta(l_1)$ (c,d) of the leading lepton for the nominal value of the f_{T2}/Λ^4 parameter in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements (a,c) and the fiducial region (b,d). Shown are the SM prediction, the decomposed LIN and QUAD EFT contributions and their sum, labelled SUM, together with the prediction of an independently simulated sample of the full prediction of the SM with the EFT extension, labelled FULL. The lower panel shows the ratio of the SUM with respect to the FULL prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 94: Distributions of the number of jets in the event, $N(j)$ (a,b), and the transverse momentum, $p_T(j_1)$ (c,d), of the leading jet for the nominal value of the f_{T2}/Λ^4 parameter in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements (a,c) and the fiducial region (b,d). Shown are the SM prediction, the decomposed LIN and QUAD EFT contributions and their sum, labelled SUM, together with the prediction of an independently simulated sample of the full prediction of the SM with the EFT extension, labelled FULL. The lower panel shows the ratio of the SUM with respect to the FULL prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 95: Distributions of the invariant mass of the leading lepton pair, m_{ll} (a,b), and the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system, m_{WW} (c,d), for the nominal value of the f_{T2}/Λ^4 parameter in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements (a,c) and the fiducial region (b,d). Shown are the SM prediction, the decomposed LIN and QUAD EFT contributions and their sum, labelled SUM, together with the prediction of an independently simulated sample of the full prediction of the SM with the EFT extension, labelled FULL. The lower panel shows the ratio of the SUM with respect to the FULL prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 96: Distributions of the invariant mass, m_{jj} (a,b), and rapidity separation, ΔY_{jj} (c,d), of the tagging jet pair for the nominal value of the f_{T2}/Λ^4 parameter in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements (a,c) and the fiducial region (b,d). Shown are the SM prediction, the decomposed LIN and QUAD EFT contributions and their sum, labelled SUM, together with the prediction of an independently simulated sample of the full prediction of the SM with the EFT extension, labelled FULL. The lower panel shows the ratio of the SUM with respect to the FULL prediction. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

3 Validation of the Scaling of EFT Contributions

Parameter value x [TeV ⁻⁴]	Generator cross-section [fb]	$\frac{\sigma(S02=x)}{\sigma(S02=8 \text{ TeV}^{-4})}$	Fiducial cross-section [fb]	$\frac{\sigma(S02=x)}{\sigma(S02=8 \text{ TeV}^{-4})}$
Linear contribution:				
2.0	-0.038 ± 0.001	0.25 ± 0.03	-0.003 ± 0.000	0.23 ± 0.12
4.0	-0.076 ± 0.001	0.50 ± 0.02	-0.007 ± 0.001	0.49 ± 0.12
8.0	-0.153 ± 0.003	—	-0.015 ± 0.001	—
-12.0	0.229 ± 0.005	-1.50 ± 0.03	0.021 ± 0.002	-1.43 ± 0.12
12.0	-0.229 ± 0.005	1.50 ± 0.03	-0.023 ± 0.002	1.58 ± 0.11
-16.0	0.305 ± 0.006	-2.00 ± 0.03	0.029 ± 0.002	-2.00 ± 0.11
16.0	-0.305 ± 0.006	2.00 ± 0.03	-0.027 ± 0.002	1.82 ± 0.12
Quadratic contribution:				
-4.0	0.274 ± 0.001	0.25 ± 0.01	0.032 ± 0.000	0.25 ± 0.02
-8.0	1.097 ± 0.005	1.00 ± 0.01	0.128 ± 0.002	1.00 ± 0.02
8.0	1.097 ± 0.005	—	0.127 ± 0.002	—
-12.0	2.469 ± 0.011	2.25 ± 0.01	0.291 ± 0.004	2.29 ± 0.02
-16.0	4.389 ± 0.020	4.00 ± 0.01	0.503 ± 0.007	3.96 ± 0.02

Table 1: Cross-section predictions in the generator and fiducial phase space of Ref. [5] for the decomposed LIN and QUAD contributions at different values of the f_{S02}/Λ^4 parameter. Columns three and five display the scaling factor between the cross-section prediction of the nominal parameter value $f_{S02}/\Lambda^4 = x_n = 8 \text{ TeV}^{-4}$ and each tested point. Uncertainties are the statistical errors of the MC generation only.

Parameter values (x, y) [TeV ⁻⁴]		Generator cross-section [fb]	$\frac{\sigma(S_{02}, S_1=x, y)}{\sigma(S_{02}, S_1=8, 20 \text{ TeV}^{-4})}$	Fiducial cross-section [fb]	$\frac{\sigma(S_{02}, S_1=x, y)}{\sigma(S_{02}, S_1=8, 20 \text{ TeV}^{-4})}$
S02	S1				
Cross contribution:					
-2.0	5.0	-0.087 ± 0.000	-0.06 ± 0.01	-0.010 ± 0.000	-0.06 ± 0.02
-2.0	-20.0	0.350 ± 0.002	0.25 ± 0.01	0.041 ± 0.001	0.25 ± 0.02
2.0	-30.0	-0.525 ± 0.002	-0.38 ± 0.01	-0.059 ± 0.001	-0.36 ± 0.02
2.0	30.0	0.525 ± 0.002	0.38 ± 0.01	0.060 ± 0.001	0.36 ± 0.02
2.0	40.0	0.699 ± 0.003	0.50 ± 0.01	0.079 ± 0.001	0.48 ± 0.02
-4.0	-5.0	0.175 ± 0.001	0.13 ± 0.01	0.020 ± 0.000	0.12 ± 0.02
-4.0	-10.0	0.349 ± 0.002	0.25 ± 0.01	0.040 ± 0.001	0.24 ± 0.02
-4.0	10.0	-0.350 ± 0.002	-0.25 ± 0.01	-0.040 ± 0.001	-0.24 ± 0.02
-4.0	-20.0	0.699 ± 0.003	0.50 ± 0.01	0.080 ± 0.001	0.49 ± 0.02
4.0	-20.0	-0.700 ± 0.003	-0.50 ± 0.01	-0.081 ± 0.001	-0.49 ± 0.02
-8.0	-10.0	0.700 ± 0.003	0.50 ± 0.01	0.081 ± 0.001	0.49 ± 0.02
-8.0	-20.0	1.398 ± 0.006	1.00 ± 0.01	0.161 ± 0.002	0.98 ± 0.02
8.0	-20.0	-1.398 ± 0.006	-1.00 ± 0.01	-0.162 ± 0.002	-0.98 ± 0.02
8.0	20.0	1.398 ± 0.007	—	0.165 ± 0.002	—
-8.0	-30.0	2.097 ± 0.010	1.50 ± 0.01	0.245 ± 0.003	1.48 ± 0.02
8.0	30.0	2.097 ± 0.010	1.50 ± 0.01	0.236 ± 0.003	1.43 ± 0.02
12.0	-5.0	-0.525 ± 0.002	-0.38 ± 0.01	-0.060 ± 0.001	-0.36 ± 0.02
-12.0	10.0	-1.048 ± 0.005	-0.75 ± 0.01	-0.118 ± 0.002	-0.71 ± 0.02
12.0	-30.0	-3.147 ± 0.014	-2.25 ± 0.01	-0.355 ± 0.005	-2.15 ± 0.02
-12.0	-40.0	4.197 ± 0.019	3.00 ± 0.01	0.482 ± 0.007	2.92 ± 0.02
12.0	40.0	4.197 ± 0.019	3.00 ± 0.01	0.489 ± 0.007	2.96 ± 0.02
16.0	-20.0	-2.794 ± 0.013	-2.00 ± 0.01	-0.328 ± 0.004	-1.99 ± 0.02
16.0	20.0	2.800 ± 0.013	2.00 ± 0.01	0.322 ± 0.004	1.95 ± 0.02
16.0	30.0	4.191 ± 0.019	3.00 ± 0.01	0.480 ± 0.007	2.91 ± 0.02
-16.0	-40.0	5.591 ± 0.026	4.00 ± 0.01	0.648 ± 0.009	3.93 ± 0.02
-16.0	40.0	-5.593 ± 0.026	-4.00 ± 0.01	-0.632 ± 0.009	-3.83 ± 0.02
16.0	-40.0	-5.593 ± 0.026	-4.00 ± 0.01	-0.644 ± 0.009	-3.90 ± 0.02
16.0	40.0	5.591 ± 0.026	4.00 ± 0.01	0.650 ± 0.009	3.94 ± 0.02

Table 2: Cross-section predictions in the generator and fiducial phase space of Ref. [5] for the decomposed CROSS contribution at different values of the parameter pair $f_{S_{02}}/\Lambda^4 - f_{S_1}/\Lambda^4$. Columns four and six display the scaling factor between the cross-section prediction of the nominal parameter value $f_{S_{02}}/\Lambda^4 = x_n = 8 \text{ TeV}^{-4}$ and each tested point. Uncertainties are the statistical errors of the MC generation only.

Figure 97: Kinematic distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system and tagging jets of the LIN contribution for different values of the f_{S1}/Λ^4 parameter. Shown are the pseudorapidity of the leading lepton $\eta(l_1)$ (a), and the the invariant mass of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system (b), the number of jets in the event, $N(j)$ (c), and the rapidity separation of the tagging jets, ΔY_{jj} (d). The distributions are normalised to the unit area. The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements. The lower panel shows the ratio with respect to the nominal value. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow. The first bin includes the underflow if appropriate.

Figure 98: Kinematic distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system and tagging jets of the QUAD contribution for different values of the f_{S1}/Λ^4 parameter. Shown are the pseudorapidity of the leading lepton $\eta(l_1)$ (a), and the the invariant mass of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system (b), the number of jets in the event, $N(j)$ (c), and the rapidity separation of the tagging jets, ΔY_{jj} (d). The distributions are normalised to the unit area. The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements. The lower panel shows the ratio with respect to the nominal value. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow. The first bin includes the underflow if appropriate.

Figure 99: Kinematic distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system of the LIN contribution for different values of the f_{S02}/Λ^4 parameter. Shown are the transverse momentum of the leading lepton $p_T(l_1)$ (a), its pseudorapidity $\eta(l_1)$ (b), and the the invariant mass of the leading lepton pair, m_{ll} (c), and the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system, m_{WW} (d). The distributions are normalised to the unit area. The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements. The lower panel shows the ratio with respect to the nominal value. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow. The first bin includes the underflow if appropriate.

Figure 100: Kinematic distributions related to the tagging jets of the LIN contribution for different values of the f_{S02}/Λ^4 parameter. Shown are the transverse momentum of the leading jet $p_T(j_1)$ (a), the number of jets in the event, $N(j)$ (b), the the invariant mass, m_{jj} (c), and rapidity separation, ΔY_{jj} (d) of the tagging jet pair. The distributions are normalised to the unit area. The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements. The lower panel shows the ratio with respect to the nominal value. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 101: Kinematic distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system of the QUAD contribution for different values of the f_{S02}/Λ^4 parameter. Shown are the transverse momentum of the leading lepton $p_T(l_1)$ (a), its pseudorapidity $\eta(l_1)$ (b), and the the invariant mass of the leading lepton pair, m_{ll} (c), and the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system (d). The distributions are normalised to the unit area. The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements. The lower panel shows the ratio with respect to the nominal value. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow. The first bin includes the underflow if appropriate.

Figure 102: Kinematic distributions related to the tagging jets of the QUAD contribution for different values of the f_{S02}/Λ^4 parameter. Shown are the transverse momentum of the leading jet $p_T(j_1)$ (a), the number of jets in the event, $N(j)$ (b), the invariant mass, m_{jj} (c), and rapidity separation, ΔY_{jj} (d) of the tagging jet pair. The distributions are normalised to the unit area. The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements. The lower panel shows the ratio with respect to the nominal value. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 103: Kinematic distributions related to the leptonic decay products of the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system of the CROSS contribution for different values of the parameter pair $f_{S02}/\Lambda^4 - f_{S1}/\Lambda^4$. Shown are the transverse momentum of the leading lepton $p_T(l_1)$ (a), its pseudorapidity $\eta(l_1)$ (b), and the the invariant mass of the leading lepton pair, m_l (c), and the $W^\pm W^\pm$ system (d). The distributions are normalised to the unit area. The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements. The lower panel shows the ratio with respect to the nominal value. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

Figure 104: Kinematic distributions related to the tagging jets of the QUAD contribution for different values of the parameter pair $f_{S02}/\Lambda^4 - f_{S1}/\Lambda^4$. Shown are the transverse momentum of the leading jet $p_T(j_1)$ (a), the number of jets in the event, $N(j)$ (b), the the invariant mass, m_{jj} (c), and rapidity separation, ΔY_{jj} (d) of the tagging jet pair. The distributions are normalised to the unit area. The nominal value is shown in green. The distributions are shown in a loose region including all events with exactly two leptons and no further requirements. The lower panel shows the ratio with respect to the nominal value. Uncertainties are statistical uncertainties from the MC generation only. The last bin includes the overflow.

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